

[View this email in your browser](#)

Welcome to our October 2021 newsletter

Our Summer School 2021 - online and self-paced 6th September to 5th November - is now almost halfway through. To mark this there will be the opportunity for attendees to socialise on Thursday 7th October UTC 11:00 and 23:00 - see below for details.

Read on to hear about the latest and very successful Data Stewardship events held virtually at the National Open Research Forum, Ireland and Gdańsk University of Technology. Plus, details of two further DS events taking place in November and December - be sure to apply if you meet the criteria - deadline 15th October.

What about winning CAD\$1,000 in the WDS-ITO Data Prize Competition? All details below and join Hugh Shanahan on Zoom on 14th October for an explanation!

We have our regular alumni profiles, this edition with Mesfin Diro and Mariana Cubero and our instructor profile is Marcela Alfaro Córdoba.

And finally, an update on the Glosario Project - find out how to get involved and contribute with your language to this language dictionary for Data Science.

2021 Research Data Science Summer School Social Event

An ICTP Virtual Meeting, Trieste, Italy

Asia, Africa, Europe Thursday 7th October UTC 11:00 - join [here](#)

Americas Thursday 7th October UTC 23:00 - join [here](#)

SciDataCon 2021 and RDA Plenary 18

Virtual SciDataCon 2021

The international conference for scrutiny and discussion of the frontier issues of data in research.

18th to 28th October.

Free registration and further details [here](#).

RDA Virtual Plenary 18

Bringing together a unique community of data science professionals from multiple disciplines and domains through working meetings of the RDA Working and Interest Groups and Birds of Feather meetings for new potential groups.

3-11 November 2021

Registration (reduced rate for students and LMICs) and further details [here](#).

Data Stewardship Training - Ireland

In mid-July, Ireland's [National Open Research Forum](#) (NORF), [FAIRsFAIR](#) and [EOSC Synergy](#) delivered a [three-day workshop](#) to support the development of data stewardship skills among staff in higher education institutions and other research performing organisations in Ireland.

The training was targeted at those within institutions who are engaged in providing support and training on research data management (RDM) and FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) data. We were pleased to welcome 39 participants from a range of institutions across Ireland. In total, 28 Irish institutions were represented, including universities, institutes of technology or technological universities, government agencies, research funding organisations, and national research infrastructure providers.

Workshop summary

stewardship supports these aims through training. Particular attention was paid to understanding the national context, the development of resources to meet needs within one's own institution, and where data stewardship roles or services fit in with related roles and services such as IT services or research support. A course development activity gave an opportunity to consider how to develop and offer RDM and FAIR data training with reference to common pedagogical frameworks. RDM service maturity and continued development within institutions were also discussed, facilitated through the use of the [Research Infrastructure Self-Evaluation](#) (RISE) model. In breakout sessions, a series of Data Management Plan (DMP) case studies were reviewed, with discussion covering suggestions for DMP improvements and potential roadblocks to implementing the plans.

The final session included a discussion on takeaway messages and actions that participants could take to foster data stewardship at their institutions. Several participants stated that they now felt less alone and indicated a desire to work more collaboratively in the future at a national level. There was also a realisation that core to the sustainable development of RDM services is buy-in across related services within institutions and that RDM and FAIR data support is not the sole domain of libraries. Many highlighted that there remain significant gaps in the knowledge, awareness and skills of the research community. Feedback also advocated the need for the support of senior management within institutions, who may not be fully aware of the implications of evolving funder and publisher requirements with regard to RDM, FAIR, and the need for Data Stewards to provide key expertise.

As a first step towards a nationally coordinated approach to building capacity and a community of Data Stewards, the idea of a data stewardship network was put to the participants of the workshop. The suggestion was warmly welcomed, particularly as many of those currently supporting RDM and FAIR within Irish HEIs or RPOs are working independently or in a small team. Immediate feedback included a number of potential actions and activities that such a network could support, such as peer learning, development of shared training materials, advocacy for RDM and FAIR at a national level, and joint events for awareness-raising and training for data professionals and researchers. While the network has yet to formally coalesce, participants were encouraged to sign up to an existing [RDM mailing list](#), opening a channel of communication for those providing data stewardship advice and training around Ireland.

Dr Daniel Bangert, DRI (National Open Research Coordinator) and Dr Aoife Coffey, UCC (NORF FAIR Working Group Co-Chair)

Full article [here](#).

What was your motivation for attending the workshop?

My main motivation is that I work in Data Science at [ICHEC](#), and unlike most of my colleagues, have generally been more concerned about the data than computational requirements. However, with the advances in technology, particularly AI models, high-end computation is getting more and more data-centric, and we have started hosting large datasets ourselves. We also expect that this activity is going to grow over time, meaning that we will need to provide some form of data stewardship. In addition, we expect that some academic/research partners might rely on us to manage a project's data products in compliance with EU funding requirements. This is why the workshop was so timely for me, as I will likely be expected to be the one providing the guidance. With both personal and professional interest in data ethics (I develop AI models for a living), I am interested in the promotion of FAIR and Open Data, which the workshop discussed.

To improve my data stewardship knowledge, share experience and participate in the small but growing community of Data Stewards in Ireland.

I attended the workshop because of the speakers, content and relevance to my role of providing RDM support. I was also interested to meet fellow participants who work in similar roles in Ireland.

To improve my FAIR data stewardship and the service I offer to researchers, with the ultimate overarching aim of normalising FAIR research data.

What was your key takeaway from the workshop?

There is a critical lack of formal data stewardship services. I have seen it first-hand in the project I have been involved with, but the case studies highlighted to me that this was an even more general problem than I assumed. Even if full-time stewards are unlikely to happen in the near future, training and part-time stewardship would go a long way to help our research community in publishing/maintaining their data products, which are fast becoming an alternative to papers as an expected research output.

We need lots more events like this if support for Irish research is to keep up with international developments in the area of Data Stewardship.

There is a great RDM support network evolving in Ireland and we can all learn from and support each other.

That those involved in all areas of FAIR data stewardship, training and proliferation have similar questions on how we can do it better, what resources are available and how we can standardise tools and requirements to measure our level of success. Also that there is a desire to have a community of practice

Data Stewardship Training - Gdańsk, Poland

The CODATA-RDA Schools instructors together with FAIRsFAIR, EOSC-Pillar, EOSC Synergy and Gdańsk University of Technology Library and the Open Science Competence Center, created in the framework of Bridge of Data project (MOST DANYCH project) at Gdańsk Tech Library, delivered a three day train-the-trainer workshop, from 6th to 10th September 2021.

A key aim of the workshop was to empower a network of peers where best practices are exchanged and where those with more experience can share their knowledge with those just getting started.

The workshop combined a series of theoretical and practical sessions, where participants were given the opportunity to interact and get to know other colleagues and exchange their experience in supporting researchers with RDM. The workshop aimed to introduce participants as data stewards to the key concepts and drivers for Open Science, RDM and FAIR principles, to enable the resulting network of practitioners in peer institutions who can collaborate, work and learn together. Participants were also introduced to key concepts of pedagogy and were able to put these in practice with a brief course design and development activity. In addition, attendees were asked to reflect on their own role as data stewards and got to evaluate the existing training offer and the status of RDM services in their respective institutions in perspective of training their members in the future.

Most of the participants had been in their data steward role (often managing data steward tasks besides regular duties) for less than 6 months and work on their own or in teams of less than 5 people. The workshop met the expectations of the participants, who had join with an interest to learn more about:

- the range of skills and knowledge associated with data stewardship,
- political drivers for RDM, FAIR and Open Data,
- how to explain the difference between FAIR and Open Data to researchers,
- how to provide and develop effective training using open learning resources,
- how to implement RDM services and advance FAIR data within their organization.

However, attendees identified also gaps and areas of improvement to support research activities in their respective institutions i.e. lack the required data

trainings on RDM, DMPs as well as they confirmed the need of developing local peer network.

Participants valued the interactive and hands-on approach of the workshop and the networking opportunity that was offered. The event gathered more than 30 participants from the emerging RDM support staff community in the country. The workshop was conducted in English although there was a chance to speak Polish during all practical sessions as each break out room had the local moderator, a member of the Open Science Competence Center at Gdańsk Tech Library, to feedback in English.

The purpose of the workshop therefore was to provide better understanding on data stewardship, research data management process and support the development of data stewardship skills among staff in universities and other research institutions in Poland.

Katarzyna Dudek, Piotr Krajewski

Testimonials:

„It is a great opportunity to get knowledge and skills about teaching others how to be a data steward.”

„There are too few such training!”

„The idea of sharing knowledge and experience regarding data stewards training is very important for our University.”

„I'm looking forward to the next workshop☺”

Alumni Profile

Mesfin Diro

volunteer to be an instructor. When I looked at the details, I filled out the form because I can teach things like R, Python, Shell. After that, I forgot about it because there was no feedback from them. One day on an afternoon, an e-mail was sent to me by Anelda van der Walt with the content apologies for waiting long. She had asked me if I can participate in data carpentry happening in Ethiopia. I immediately responded to her e-mail so that in October 2017, I contributed to the workshop as a helper. After that, I completed two days of online instructor training and toured various training sessions under the auspices of GIZ at different Ethiopian Universities.

My participation in CODATA-RDA is closely attached to The-Carpentries (Data-Carpentry, and Software Carpentry) workshops engagement. At the end of 2017, we wanted to take The-Carpentries workshops one step further. Dr. Margaret Gfrerer already knew CODATA-RDA, so she suggested bringing the summer school into Ethiopia. When we looked at the CODATA-RDA Summer Curriculum, we started talking to the officials because it fit our idea. Hence, I was able to attend the ICTP Summer School in Trieste, Italy, in 2018, aiming to have the CODATA-RDA in Ethiopia. The CODATA-RDA Summer School was under preparation in October 2018, Kigali, Rwanda. The organizers asked me to participate in the school at ICTP, and I gladly accepted and participated as an instructor in the event.

Two days after the conclusion of the Rwandan summer school, I went to the International Data Week 18 conference in Gaborone. In Gaborone, we had a discussion with CODATA-RDA officials about when and how to conduct the school in Ethiopia. Finally, we agreed that the Computational Data Science program at Addis Ababa University, where I work, could host the CODATA-RDA school of research and data science. As a result, I was able to participate as an instructor and organizer in the CODATA-RDA Summer School sponsored by the African Academy of Science in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia from June 3 - 14, 2019. I had also participated as a virtual helper on an online session due to the COVID19 pandemic in 2020.

Finally, I hope that I will be able to make a significant contribution to CODATA-RDA's summer school in the future too.

Alumni Profile

Mariana Cubero

I am a statistician based in Costa Rica. Most of my work is related to data analysis and data visualization and big data to answer business questions and sales prediction models. My academic research interests include urban mobility, queue waiting time prediction, generalized linear models, sales forecasting and consumer engagement. Right after I finished college, I started working in the National Center for High Technology in Costa Rica in collaboration with the Program Estado de la Nación. There my research was mostly related with urban mobility patterns and the relationship with social indicators. Also, there I had the opportunity to teach programming workshops of statistical analysis and data visualization to students and professors from public universities in my country. The 2019 CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Summer School held in Trieste, Italy was a great opportunity to explore and learn new teaching techniques, to learn new data science tools. In the same year we were hosts to the CODATA-RDA Research Data Science School in Costa Rica for the first time. That time I collaborated as an instructor and helped with the organization. Since then, I have continued to network with the CODATA Alumni via the CODATA-connect working group, as well as connect with other participants of #dataSanJosé19 from Latin America where we had organized many activities such as workshops, essays contests, webinars, etc. The Schools allowed me to understand better the importance of open science and improved my research skills. The School brought major growth to my academic and professional career.

**Data Steward Instructor Training Workshops - apply now -
deadline 15th October UTC 23:59**

a professional working in research data support roles in Higher Education or Research Institutions?

or

an individual with a research background considering a change to a data support role? This Includes individuals working directly with a research team with a deep background in a research discipline or someone working at an institutional level with a broader background. Applications from individuals who have recently started work in this area and are looking to expand their network are prioritised.

[FAIRsFAIR](#) and [EOSC Synergy](#) will deliver two data steward instructor training workshops over the weeks of November 29th and December 6th. The purpose of these workshops is to support the development of data stewardship skills among staff in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and other research performing organisations. A key aim of each workshop is to empower those new to the role and to help foster a network of peers where best practices are exchanged and those with more experience can share their knowledge with those just getting started.

During each workshop the following topics will be covered:

- Introduction to FAIR, Research Data Management (RDM) and Open Science
- Tools to assess awareness of the FAIR principles
- Data Management Planning
- Understanding Responsible and Open Research
- Assessing and planning levels of RDM service provision
- Pedagogy in the context of teaching the above and related topics

A preliminary programme can be found [here](#) and information from previous training workshops can be read [here](#).

The workshops will be run remotely using a combination of webinars and team-based activities.

Applications from all regions to attend the workshops are accepted with an emphasis on applicants from Europe. Each workshop will be run on three half days over the duration of a week. ***Successful applicants must commit to attending all of the sessions for the workshop they are assigned to.*** The two workshops have the following start times

- November 29th, December 1st, 3rd - 09:00 UTC
- December 6th, 8th, 10th - 12:00 UTC

[Subscribe](#)[Past Issues](#)[Translate](#) ▼

following technology platforms will be used - Zoom, Google Drive (account required), Menti. The fairdataforum.org will be used to facilitate communication between trainers and participants during and after the event which requires pre-event registration.

Further details and application [here](#).

Deadline 15th October 23:59 UTC

Instructor Profile

Marcela Alfaro Córdoba

I am a Teaching Assistant Professor of Statistics at the University of California, Santa Cruz. My work has two emphases: one is related to improving teaching methods for statistics and data science to undergraduate and graduate students, and the other one is on applied statistics, finding ways to analyze scientific data -- mostly related to the environment -- in an efficient and reproducible way. Being an applied statistician helps me base my class material on my experiences collaborating with different scientific fields.

My first contact with the CODATA-RDA schools was back in 2017. I applied to the Summer School in Trieste that year, right after I graduated from my Ph.D., and I was lucky to be admitted. I remember going through all the material from the school thinking: how did I finish my dissertation without knowing anything about version control? How did I work on my first papers without thinking about reproducibility nor having a data management plan? That being said, the material was not the most important lesson during those two memorable weeks. The opportunity to work with my classmates and instructors, learning from them, from their home countries and institutions was the most valuable. Learning from them how to be an early career researcher in countries with less resources to do so, informed my career path in Costa Rica, and beyond. Some of the ideas about how to create curriculum in research institutions with all sorts

After that, I was very excited to be involved in the schools, and I decided to volunteer to be a helper in the first school in the Americas: the ICTP-SAIFR in Sao Paulo, Brazil, that was organized at the end of that same year. At that point I was working as a new faculty for the University of Costa Rica, and being a helper allowed me to learn more early career researchers like me, this time mostly from Latin American countries, and share stories about our research institutions in the region, and talk about the common challenges that we had. At the end of that school, the group of co-chairs at that point offered me a seat to also be a co-chair of the schools, and I was very excited to accept the challenge and honor.

Being a co-chair for the last four years has opened a lot of doors for me, and for Costa Rica, where I am originally from. First, it introduced me to RDA Plenaries, and thanks to that, and to the support from RDA USA, Costa Rica was the host of the 17th RDA Plenary. This allowed a lot of colleagues from Costa Rica to connect with RDA networks, and this has resulted in tremendous gains for the research data community in the country. Second, the region of the RDA Americas chapter is on its way to be created, and this could lead to North-South collaborations in terms of building human resource capacity related to research data. This includes an initiative to translate our materials into French, Spanish and Portuguese, which is still in the works. Third, we were able to organize two schools in Costa Rica: one RDS Summer school in CeNAT, San José, and another one for Data Stewards at the Universidad Nacional de Costa Rica.

Data Prize Competition - open to all!!

Inaugural WDS-ITO Data Prize

Deadline 1st December 2021

The World Data System International Technology Office (WDS-ITO) is running a competition to highlight the use of WDS [Regular](#) and [Network](#) member data in Virtual Research Environments. **2 cash prizes of CAD\$1,000 each will be awarded.** In addition to the prize, the winners will be recognised in early spring 2022 and their achievements highlighted on the WDS website.

They want to know more about how researchers, students, developers, and data scientists facilitate the pipeline of data between repositories and analytics engines, and they are inviting you to show them your solutions. The purpose of the award is to incentivise and document innovative use, analysis, or

Further details and entry form [here](#) and Hugh Shanahan will also be giving an explanation of the competition on **14th October UTC 11:00**. To join the Zoom call click [here](#) - meeting ID 851 9365 9022 | passcode 957405.

Maybe you want to enter as a team? If you do enter, please let the instructors know at [dataschools \[at\] codata.org](mailto:dataschools@codata.org) so they can assist in any way.

Glosario

An open source glossary of terms used in data science

Crossing the chasm between the sand dunes of Namibia's Kalahari and the glaciers of Alaska

Unfortunately, this has nothing to do with ecology or even geology. Not even climate change or saving whales. It is all about what it would take to understand the similarities and the differences between these two very different worlds and it is about noticing the similarities.

Imagine, you have lived your entire life among the sand dunes of the [Kalahari desert](#), there right on the edge of Namibia, and you suddenly get to travel to Alaska to have a look at the [Mendenhall Glacier](#). You will most probably not dress warm enough but most of all you will be dumbstruck and in awe of a landscape that is so different ... but which also share many similarities if these were explained to you. Going back home you lose your camera and you are on your own ... Your friends and family would like to share in your experience and you would like them to understand what you saw. What do you do? You make use of words, using the language that you share, you explain as best you can! If your imagination could help you picture this solution to a predicament your reason will help you relate to [Glosario](#).

Glosario is an open source glossary of terms used in data science. It is available online and also as a library in both R and Python. By adding glossary keys to a lesson's metadata, authors can indicate what the lesson teaches, what learners ought to know before they start, and where they can go to find that knowledge. Authors can also use the library's functions to insert consistent hyperlinks for terms and definitions in their lessons in any of several (human) languages.

Most people may think this project is about creating new terms and find that painful. In actual fact it is rather about the **explanation** of the term in your mother tongue. If you are able to create a new term that is first prize but it is the explanation, the definition which is

[Subscribe](#)[Past Issues](#)[Translate](#) ▼

with the technology – we have a recipe to make it all really easy.

We experimented with the process recently (July 2021) at the Pretoria Data Science School and we were able to add two African languages ([SeTswana](#) and [isiXhosa](#)) to the mix. No, we unfortunately, did not translate all the terms but we think we have fine-tuned the process to ensure that the speakers of the language are happy with the translation that is uploaded. It is therefore time to start working and we need to contact any alumni interested in how this could work. We have a [defined list](#) of Data Science School Terms (<100 of them) plus their definitions available. Translations are added to the repository one at a time so, no need to think this has to be done in one go. This means that if we share the task it could be completed in less than three months! This would mean that as of January 2022 anyone preparing lessons in R, Python and a few other languages would be able to link in specific languages to help trainees understand the jargon which is being used. It is all about shifting the sand dune one grain at a time or letting that glacier slide, ice crystal by ice crystal!

Please add your name to our [list of participants](#) and we'll take it from there.

You could also contact any one of the project leads, listed below, if you would like to participate in the project.

Andiswa Bakulu, SADiLaR: Andiswa.Bukula@nwu.ac.za

Kalonji Abondance Tshisekedi, WiTS University: abondancekalonji08@gmail.com

Ola Karrar, University of Khartoum: ozkarrar2@gmail.com

Martie van Deventer, University of Pretoria: vandeventer.martie@gmail.com

Our mailing address is:

dataschools@codata.org

[Unsubscribe from this list](#)

Subscribe

Past Issues

Translate ▼

[why did I get this?](#) [unsubscribe from this list](#) [update subscription preferences](#)

CODATA-RDA Schools for Research Data Science · Rutherford Appleton Laboratory · Harwell, Didcot · Oxford, Oxfordshire OX11 0QX ·
United Kingdom

